

Enhancing Organizational Antifragility through Financial and Market Strength Capabilities

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Abstract. This study investigates the antifragility of organizations, especially in strategic sectors highly exposed to disruptive events. Based on a qualitative approach with case studies in the wine and textile sectors in Portugal, the findings indicate that financial and market strength, as resilience capabilities, operate interdependently and are reinforced by digital maturity and supply chain integration. Companies with financial robustness and strong market intelligence tend to be more agile in strategically investing and reallocating resources during crises. The research adopts an expanded definition of antifragility, which incorporates resilience, innovation, and strategic reconfiguration in the face of disruptions. It concludes that organizational antifragility results from the articulation of financial resources, market intelligence, and digital collaboration, offering a sustainable competitive advantage in the face of uncertainty. The study contributes to theoretical debates and provides practical recommendations for managers and policymakers.

Keywords: Resilience Capabilities. Antifragility. Financial Strength. Market Strength

1. Introduction

In an increasingly volatile, complex, and interconnected world, organizations face growing pressure to develop capabilities that go beyond the mere ability to withstand external shocks. Climate emergencies, pandemics, political and trade crises, and technological uncertainties demand organizational forms capable of operating with stability, adapting quickly, and ideally evolving positively in the face of disruptions. In this context, academic and managerial interest in the concepts of resilience and antifragility has grown, particularly as applied to organisations that integrate human intelligence and collaborative digital systems in their structures and decision-making processes.

In this context, this article investigates how financial strength and market strength capabilities interact to reinforce the antifragility of organizations, especially in strategic sectors highly exposed to disruptive events. The analysis is grounded in the theoretical foundations of dynamic capabilities [22, 2], organizational resilience [20, 3], and disruption management in supply chains [15, 4], aligning with an integrative perspective that views these capabilities as complementary elements to generate adaptive advantages in high-uncertainty environments.

Although the literature often differentiates between the concepts of resilience and antifragility, this study considers them in an integrated manner. According to [14] and [20], resilience refers to an organization's ability to withstand disturbances and return to its prior state of functioning. Antifragility, as proposed by [21], goes further, it represents the ability to benefit from disorder, learning, and strengthening from it. For

the purposes of this research, we adopt an expanded and operational definition of antifragility that incorporates resilience, considering it the ability of organizations to persist, adapt, or transform in the face of change and disruptive events [13, 19, 24]. This integrated approach enables us to observe not only resistance or recovery, but also the innovation, learning, and strategic reconfiguration processes triggered by external events.

Theoretically, this study contributes to emerging debates on resilience and antifragility by proposing an integrated analytical model that links financial and market capabilities in organizational environments. Additionally, by considering antifragility as a continuum of strategic response, from persistence to transformation, the study broadens the understanding of organizational adaptation mechanisms in complex and unstable environments [5, 24].

Based on that, the research is guided by the following question: How do financial strength and market strength capabilities contribute to the antifragility of organizations in the face of disruptive events? To investigate this question, we conducted a qualitative multiple-case study in two strategic sectors of the Portuguese economy: the wine and textile industries. These sectors were chosen due to their historical, social, and economic relevance in Portugal, as well as their high exposure to challenges such as climate change, global supply chain disruptions, and sustainability-related regulatory transitions. Both also display interorganizational collaborative dynamics and increasing levels of digitalization, making them representative of organizations in real contexts.

Data collection involved three complementary qualitative techniques: (i) analysis of secondary data, including sector association reports, strategic documents, scientific publications, and governmental sources; (ii) direct observation of organizational practices during technical visits and sectoral events; and (iii) focus groups with representatives from companies, support institutions, public entities, and experts from both sectors (one focus group per sector). The combination of these approaches enabled us to capture different dimensions of the phenomenon under study, focusing on narratives, practices, and perceptions regarding responsiveness and transformation in the face of crises.

Organizations, focus of this study, are characterized by the combination of human intelligence and algorithms, decision-support systems, and collaborative digital platforms. The use of technologies such as artificial intelligence, IoT, analytics, and blockchain does not replace human action but complements it, enhancing monitoring, forecasting, and strategic response capabilities [1, 12]. In such organizations, intangible resources such as data and shared knowledge become central to building resilience and, as we argue, antifragility.

The results reveal that financial and market strength capabilities do not operate in isolation but mutually reinforce one another in building antifragile organizational responses. For example, companies with financial robustness were able to invest in innovation, digitalization, and supplier diversification during the crisis, while those with well-developed market intelligence quickly redirected these resources to strategic areas. Moreover, companies with trusted relationships with clients and partners were able to renegotiate deadlines, adjust offerings, and maintain revenue during critical moments, which in turn bolstered their financial stability.

2. Literature Review

2.1 From Dynamic Capabilities to Resilience Capabilities

The theory of dynamic capabilities [22] emphasizes strategic adaptability as a key factor for achieving sustainable competitive advantage in volatile and uncertain markets. According to [2], builds on this by systematizing the concept and proposing that dynamic capabilities are composed of multiple dimensions that work together to enable continuous adaptation.

In contexts of extreme uncertainty, such as health crises or geopolitical shifts, dynamic capabilities become essential not only for maintaining competitiveness but also for enabling innovation and strategic transformation. [5, 24] argue that such capabilities can be replicable in high-velocity environments, but competitive advantage lies in an organization's ability to apply them with agility and at the right moment. This perspective is directly linked to resilience, as the rapid and effective reconfiguration in the face of disruptions is a clear indicator of dynamic capabilities in action.

Considering this, resilience is the ability of an organization to withstand, absorb, and recover from disruptive events while maintaining acceptable levels of functioning and performance. According to [20], supply chain resilience involves capabilities of adaptation, response, and recovery, which enable firms not only to endure shocks but also to learn and evolve from them. This perspective is expanded by [3], who introduce dimensions such as robustness, redundancy, rapidity, and resources, forming a multidimensional framework to assess resilience in complex systems.

The literature suggests that resilience should be understood as a combination of structural and relational competencies. [24] highlight factors such as agility, visibility, and flexibility as essential for a resilient supply chain. Furthermore, emphasize that resilience is a dynamic process, involving continuous adaptation to changing environmental conditions and requiring organizational routines oriented toward learning.

Building on this theoretical foundation, this study specifically examines the dynamic capabilities of market strength and financial strength, understood as critical enablers of organizational resilience and antifragility. In highly volatile and uncertain environments, such as those shaped by systemic crises or supply chain disruptions, these capabilities allow organizations not only to absorb shocks but also to strategically reposition themselves.

Financial strength was defined as the organization's ability to absorb financial shocks and reallocate resources, both in the short and long term, to sustain or improve performance. Elements such as liquidity, credit access, budget flexibility, and contractual renegotiation capacity emerged as key components of this dimension [8, 10]. Market strength, in turn, refers to the ability to anticipate and respond to changes in external demands and conditions, maintain stable relationships with strategic customers and suppliers, and explore new market opportunities even in adverse contexts [6, 16].

2.2 The Relationship between Resilience and Antifragility: An Integrated Approach

Over recent decades, organizational resilience has become a critical capability in environments marked by uncertainty, disruption, and volatility. Traditionally, resilience

is understood as the ability to withstand, absorb impacts, and recover, returning to a functional state after adverse events [20, 3]. However, the contemporary context, characterized by systemic crises, accelerated technological change, and complex disruptions, demands a broader and more evolutionary perspective.

In this study, we adopt an expanded and operational definition of antifragility, aligned with [24], which incorporates resilience as a foundational component. Antifragility, in this sense, is not only about overcoming adversity but about the ability to persist, adapt, and transform in the face of change and external shocks. This integrated approach allows us to observe not only resistance or recovery, but also the processes of innovation, organizational learning, and strategic reconfiguration triggered by disruption.

Resilience thus functions as an operational prerequisite for antifragility. Resilient organizations are able to maintain operations and safeguard critical assets during crises; however, only antifragile organizations can leverage such moments to evolve, creating new organizational forms, practices, and structures. While resilience focuses on robustness and a return to the status quo, antifragility emphasizes continuous improvement through adversity [21].

Recent literature has emphasized that resilience and antifragility are not dichotomous, but progressive [7]. [24] proposes that the transition from a resilient to an antifragile system depends on an organization's ability to combine intelligent redundancy, strategic experimentation, decentralized decision-making, and collaborative learning. In supply chains, this translates into practices such as multi-sourcing, digital traceability, collaborative networks, and predictive simulations [15, 4]. Moreover, by integrating the antifragility perspective, we broaden the analytical scope of resilience: from a capability for operational continuity to a lever for sustainable competitive advantage. Antifragile organizations develop, over time, an adaptive memory, based on the intelligent collection, dissemination, and use of information, that allows them to turn threats into strategic opportunities.

Therefore, rather than treating resilience and antifragility as separate capabilities, this research supports a continuous and integrated approach, in which resilience provides the foundation, and antifragility represents a higher evolutionary stage. In contexts marked by unpredictable events, such as pandemics, wars, logistical crises, and protectionist policies, antifragile organizations are able to turn vulnerabilities into strategic opportunities. This perspective enables a better understanding of how organizations not only survive but grow stronger and innovate through disruption.

3. Methodology

This research is part of the RISE-SME project, funded by the European Union through the Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement number 101138645. The project is based on a comprehensive analysis of various resilience capabilities within industrial supply chains (adaptability & flexibility, efficiency, visibility, redundancy, market strength, financial strength, response, transform). During the interpretation of results, it was observed that market strength and financial strength capabilities consistently stood out across the cases analyzed. Considering this finding, the present study focuses specifically on an in-depth examination of these two capabilities, aiming to understand how they contribute to building organizational

resilience in the face of disruptive events.

Thus, to achieve the objective of investigating how financial strength and market strength capabilities interact to reinforce the antifragility of organizations, especially in strategic sectors highly exposed to disruptive events, we chose two economic activity sectors: the wine sector and the textile sector. According to [26], sectors can be categorized based on the essentiality index, which serves as an indicator of economic protection against the impacts of measures implemented during disruptive periods, such as the COVID-19 lockdown.

Guided by this indicator, our methodological approach focused on these two sectors at opposite ends of the spectrum: the textile sector, identified as having low essentiality, and the agri-food sector, recognized as highly essential. Within the agri-food sector, we specifically chose to analyse the wine industry for convenience.

Considering that, data collection involved three complementary qualitative techniques designed to ensure a comprehensive and contextualized understanding of resilience capabilities. This multi-method approach follows the principles of triangulation to enhance the credibility and depth of qualitative research [9, 18].

First, the analysis of secondary data included a wide array of documentary sources such as reports from industry associations, strategic documents, academic articles, and governmental publications. This type of documentary analysis is as it helps to contextualize findings and corroborate data from other sources [25].

Second, direct observation was carried out during technical visits to firms and at sectoral events such as workshops and conferences. This method allowed researchers to observe routines, behaviors, and interactions in situ, capturing tacit elements of organizational practice. As highlighted by [11], observation contributes to understanding the real-world context of organizational processes, especially those not easily articulated by participants.

Third, focus groups were conducted with stakeholders from companies, support institutions, public entities, and academic or technical experts. These group discussions enabled the collection of diverse and interactive insights on resilience strategies and sectoral responses to disruptions. According to [17], focus groups are particularly effective in exploratory research as they stimulate collective reflection, highlight consensus and divergence, and generate rich qualitative data through interaction (Table 1).

Table 1. Focus Group sessions information

Sector	Date	Local	Duration (hours)	Number of participants
Textile	November, 2024	Portugal	3,5	12
Wine	December, 2024	Portugal	2,5	11

The combination of these approaches enabled us to capture different dimensions of the phenomenon under study, focusing on narratives, practices, and perceptions regarding responsiveness and transformation in the face of crises.

4. Results and Discussion

Based on the focus groups conducted, we gathered practical insights into the

importance of financial strength and market strength as key elements of resilience in the sectors analysed (Table 2). Participants assessed, on a scale from 1 to 5, the level of development of various indicators associated with resilience capabilities. The results reveal that, in the textile sector, there is a high level of maturity in both domains, with notable scores for access to medium- and long-term financial resources (4.8) and stable relationships with clients (4.7), reflecting a scenario of structural solidity and stability in commercial relationships.

In the wine sector, participants also acknowledged the importance of financial and market strength, although with slightly lower average scores compared to the textile sector. Access to short-term financial resources (4.3) and client relationships (4.5) were positively evaluated, indicating a resilient foundation, though with greater variation across indicators. The lowest score was given to the capacity to establish new partnerships and access new markets (3.7), highlighting an opportunity for strategic development. These qualitative assessments, resulting from direct engagement with sector stakeholders, provide valuable evidence about the internal and relational capabilities that support or constrain companies' responses to disruptive events.

Table 2. Description of capabilities

	Capability	Indicator	Grade	Mean
Textile Sector	Financial Strength	have access to resources (short-term) to mitigate the impacts of supply chain interruptions	4,5	4,6
		have access to resources (medium/long-term) to invest in changes prompted by the event	4,8	
	Market Strength	have a stable relationship with suppliers	4,5	4,6
		have a stable relationship with customers	4,7	
		establish new partnerships or access new markets	4,5	
Wine Sector	Financial Strength	have access to resources (short-term) to mitigate the impacts of supply chain interruptions	4,3	4,1
		have access to resources (medium/long-term) to invest in changes prompted by the event	3,9	
	Market Strength	have a stable relationship with suppliers	4,2	4,1
		have a stable relationship with customers	4,5	
		establish new partnerships or access new markets	3,7	

4.1 Textile Sector: Conservative Resilience

From the perspective of dynamic capabilities [22], the textile sector demonstrates maturity in identifying, integrating, and reconfiguring resources to cope with disruptions. The high scores attributed to financial strength and market strength show that companies in this sector place great importance on maintaining liquidity and access to both short- and long-term resources, as well as stable relationships with clients and suppliers, while also actively seeking new partnerships and markets. These capabilities indicate a consolidated competitive position and reflect competencies to reconfigure strategies in the face of crises, reinforcing the sector's adaptability.

From the standpoint of resilience capabilities, the textile sector emphasizes preparation and rapid response to disruptive events. Financial strength allows firms to absorb shocks, while market strength helps maintain trust across the supply chain. However, transformation capability was considered less relevant, suggesting a tendency toward stability rather than radical innovation. Thus, in terms of antifragility [21], the sector appears to remain within the sphere of classical resilience, enduring and recovering, rather than advancing toward positive evolution in the face of crisis. This

may be related to the traditional character of the sector, with less agile structures for deep transformations. In this context, we propose:

Proposition 1: In traditional sectors, where the combination of financial and market strength supports solid resilience but limits organizational transformation, the result is an adaptive and conservative response to disruptions.

4.2 Wine Sector: Moving Toward Antifragility

Through the lens of dynamic capabilities, the wine sector demonstrates competencies oriented toward adapting and integrating resources in volatile contexts. Market strength capabilities, such as consolidated relationships with clients and suppliers, reveal a strategic focus on maintaining distribution channels and diversifying markets. While financial strength is also relevant, it scores slightly lower than in the textile sector, indicating some limitations in pursuing long-term strategic investments. Nonetheless, these capabilities provide a solid foundation for responding to the environmental and economic threats that characterize the sector.

In terms of resilience capabilities, the wine sector faces more systemic risks, such as environmental and political crises, which require not only recovery but continuous transformation. As such, there is potential for antifragility, as companies that adopt digital practices and new technologies may not only withstand disruptions but emerge stronger. The emphasis on sustainable practices, commercial digitalization, and adaptation to direct-to-consumer channels suggests a move toward strategic reconfiguration. In this context, we propose:

Proposition 2: In sectors highly exposed to systemic risks and external pressure for innovation, the presence of market strength combined with moderate financial strength promotes adaptation and stimulates transformation, enabling organizations to evolve toward antifragile behaviour in the face of disruptions.

4.3 Sectoral Comparison: Stability vs. Transformation

When comparing the two sectors, both value preparation and response capabilities, with financial and market strength standing out as common pillars of resilience. However, the textile sector adopts a more conservative stance, focused on stabilization and continuity, reflecting a more robust and less transformational profile. The wine sector, on the other hand, shows greater openness to adaptive transformation, integrating sustainability and digitalization dimensions that can catalyse antifragile capabilities.

While the textile sector relies heavily on internal resources and established relationships to resist shocks, the wine sector is more sensitive to external environments and more likely to reconfigure practices in response to change. From the perspective of antifragility, this positions the wine sector one step ahead, as it transforms vulnerabilities into strategic advantages. The ability to learn from adverse events and incorporate innovations suggests a more dynamic evolution potential, in contrast to the greater adaptive rigidity observed in the textile sector. In this context, we propose:

Proposition 3: Organizational resilience based on financial and market strength manifests differently depending on the sector's openness to transformation, being

conservative and stabilizing in traditional sectors (such as textiles), and evolutionary and antifragile in sectors facing environmental and technological pressures (such as wine).

Furthermore, these differences can be better understood when analysed through the lens of the essentiality index proposed by the [26], which classifies sectors based on the degree of economic protection they receive during disruptive events, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The textile sector, identified as having low essentiality, was among the first to experience operational shutdowns and among the last to resume activity [23]. This limited institutional prioritization translated into reduced access to emergency support measures, supply chain continuity, and policy-driven incentives, pushing firms to rely predominantly on internal resources, particularly financial reserves and pre-existing market relationships, to maintain operations. As a result, organizations in this sector adopted conservative resilience strategies, focused on survival and damage containment, with minimal room for experimentation or structural transformation. The high scores in financial and market strength observed in the textile sector reflect this emphasis on stability and preservation, rather than on adaptability or innovation.

In contrast, the wine sector, positioned within the broader agri-food ecosystem, was classified as highly essential, allowing it to maintain operations even during the strictest phases of lockdown. This designation resulted in greater operational continuity, preferential logistical access, and targeted institutional support, including subsidies and trade facilitation. Such conditions provided not only a safety net for firms but also a window of opportunity to invest in strategic adjustments, such as the digitalization of sales channels, reconfiguration of distribution networks, and engagement with more sustainable and resilient supply practices. Despite scoring lower in financial capacity, wine sector firms leveraged their market strength and the relative stability of institutional backing to explore transformative pathways, enabling them not just to recover, but to evolve, an essential characteristic of antifragility.

Thus, when observed through the essentiality lens, it becomes evident that institutional positioning and external support mechanisms critically shape the strategic room for manoeuvre available to firms during crises. While both sectors exhibit strong foundational capabilities, their trajectories diverge according to how their economic role is perceived and supported at the policy level. Antifragility, in this sense, is not merely a function of internal resources, but also of the enabling environment that allows organizations to take calculated risks, innovate, and grow stronger from disruption. In this context, we propose:

Proposition 4: Highly essential sectors tend to develop greater antifragility due to stronger institutional support and operational continuity during crises, while low-essentiality sectors adopt more conservative strategies, limiting their potential for transformation.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to investigate how financial strength and market strength capabilities interact to reinforce organizational antifragility, especially in strategic sectors highly exposed to disruptive events. Based on the comparative analysis between the textile and

wine sectors, it was observed that these two capabilities operate in complementary ways, though influenced by the sectoral context. In the textile sector, financial robustness and stable commercial ties support consolidated resilience, yet one that is oriented toward maintenance and recovery, with limited openness to transformation. In contrast, in the wine sector, market strength plays a central role in adaptation and innovation, while financial strength, although more limited, contributes to a more agile and evolutionary response to disruptions.

These differences can be better understood when analysed through the lens of the essentiality index proposed by the [26], which classifies sectors according to their level of economic protection during crises. The textile sector, categorized as low essentiality, faced greater restrictions and less institutional support during the pandemic, leading to more conservative resilience strategies. In contrast, the wine sector, as part of the highly essential agri-food ecosystem, benefited from greater operational continuity and external support, creating conditions for developing more transformation-oriented capabilities, a pathway that favors antifragility.

By methodologically focusing on two sectors at opposite ends of the essentiality spectrum, it was possible to demonstrate that the interaction between financial and market strength not only sustains resilience but can also act as a catalyst for antifragility, provided that the institutional environment and sectoral culture support strategic reconfiguration. In the wine sector, this interaction is evident in the ability to diversify markets, adopt technologies, and adapt to new forms of consumption. In the textile sector, however, the same combination, although solid, still operates under a predominantly defensive logic. Thus, organizational antifragility depends not only on the existence of these capabilities but also on the willingness to use them to transform vulnerabilities into strategic advantages.

From a practical standpoint, the results offer guidance for managers and policymakers. Rather than focusing exclusively on contingency plans, it is advisable to adopt capacity development approaches, with targeted investments in digital systems, flexible financial structures, and market intelligence applied to decision-making. The experience of the analysed sectors shows that building antifragility also involves co-creation with stakeholders, collaborative governance, and continuous learning from crises.

However, one limitation of this research concerns the small number of sectors analyzed, which may restrict the generalizability of the results to other industrial contexts. Additionally, the data was collected through focus groups, relying on participants' subjective perceptions, which may introduce interpretative biases. Future studies using quantitative approaches and larger samples could complement and deepen the findings presented here.

Given these limitations, future studies are recommended to expand the analysis to a larger number of sectors with varying levels of essentiality, allowing for greater generalizability of the results. Moreover, it is suggested that the propositions be tested as hypotheses with quantitative methods. The use of quantitative approaches, such as surveys or statistical models, could complement the perceptions gathered from the focus groups, providing greater robustness to the conclusions and enabling the identification of broader patterns in the interaction between organizational capabilities and antifragility across different contexts. Furthermore, comparative studies between

countries or regions with different institutional structures could also enrich the understanding of the factors that influence the strengthening of organizational antifragility in diverse contexts.

In conclusion, this research reinforces the idea that organizational antifragility results from the strategic articulation of financial and market strength, mediated by digital technologies and collaborative networks. Organizations that can harmonize these elements are better positioned not only to withstand disruptions but to emerge stronger, more innovative, and better adapted to new realities. By recognizing the value of error, instability, and transformation, these organizations stop fearing change and start using it as a source of sustainable competitive advantage.

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